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Impact of supervisor support and work schedule flexibility on job stress and turnover intention of software developers in Sri Lanka

ABSTRACT

This paper presents and discusses the results of an empirical study that investigated the impact of supervisor support and work schedule flexibility on job stress and turnover intention. In the study, supervisor support and work schedule flexibility are considered as independent variables, job stress as the mediator, and turnover intention as the dependent variable. 350 self-administered survey questionnaires were distributed among software developers full-time engaged in offshore outsourced software development firms. 232 valid responses were returned, yielding a response rate of 66%. The three-step regression analysis procedure was used to test mediation hypotheses using SPSS. It was found that job stress partially mediates the relationship between supervisor support and turnover intention. Further, it was found that job stress fully mediates the relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention. The results of the study imply that the increased levels of supervisor support could lead to decrease job stress, which subsequently could lead to decrease turnover intention. Similarly, the increased levels of work schedule flexibility could lead to decrease job stress, which subsequently could lead to decrease turnover intention.

Keywords: Job stress, Supervisor support, Work schedule flexibility

1. INTRODUCTION

Job stress is identified as an important occupational health problem (Johnson et al., 2005). Evidence suggests that high levels of unmanaged job stress not only undermine the quality, productivity, and creativity of employees but also influence employees' health, well-being, and morale (Burton et al., 2008). Therefore, some of the most important topics of research in human resource management today revolve around specific policies, practices, and programmes that appear to influence job stress (e.g., Dooris et al., 2008). When it comes to addressing stress in the workplace, there is a need to evaluate different strategies available at the organizational level to find out which strategies are effective for job stress (see Le Fevre et al., 2006). However,

very little evidence is available on which to base the organizational focused stress management strategies, and little clear information is available on the relative effectiveness of various strategies in general (see Le Fevre et al., 2006).

In the above context, this paper explores the effects of two contrasting initiatives, i.e., instrumental support (i.e., work schedule flexibility) and social support (i.e., supervisory support), on job stress. Therefore, this paper investigates the impact of supervisor support and work schedule flexibility on job stress and turnover intention. In the study, supervisor support and work schedule flexibility were considered as independent variables, job stress as the mediator, and turnover intention

as the dependent variable. Therefore, the study investigated the mediating effect of job stress on the relationship between supervisor support/work schedule flexibility and turnover intention of software developers attached to offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka.

The literature suggests that the high level of occupational identification among software developers is suggestive of an aspirant profession and a key occupation to examine in future studies of knowledge workers (Scholarios and Marks, 2004). They are identified as one of the critical resources of a country in its quest to become a technologically advanced nation. Further, they enjoy considerable labour market power, which has encouraged their mobility across organizations rather than promoting loyalty to a single organization (Scholarios and Marks, 2004). During the last decade, Sri Lanka witnessed a growth of offshore outsourced software development firms in the country. The literature provides evidence for both extensive opportunities created for software developers as well as increased stress in the workplace (Aziz, 2004; Poravi and Wickramasinghe, 2010). However, the literature suggests that attitudes of software developers towards the characteristics of work organization in the offshore outsourced sector have yet to be systematically examined (Jinadasa and Wickramasinghe, 2005). Therefore, the specific objective of the study is to investigate the impact of supervisor support and work schedule flexibility on job stress and turnover intention.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

2.1 Job Stress

Job stress is generally defined in literature as an employee's feeling of job-related hardness, tension, anxiety, frustration, worry, emotional exhaustion, and distress (Armstrong and Griffin, 2004). In other words, work-related variables (job stressors), when interpreted by the individual (cognitive interpretation), may lead to stress (Dua, 1994). Therefore, stressors denote the external force or situation acting on the individual - objective

events. Stress denotes the deformation or changes produced in the individual as a result of those forces - subjective experience of the event (Le Fevre et al., 2003).

Further, job stress is a mental and physical condition and becomes problematic when it remains unresolved because of lapses in an individual's adaptive capacity (Erkutlu and Chafra, 2006; Dua, 1994). When this happens, the individual becomes disorganized, disoriented, and therefore, becomes less able to cope (Amarakoon and Wickramasinghe, 2011; Cooper and Marshall, 1976; Erkutlu and Chafra, 2006; Le Fevre et al., 2006). The literature suggests that a high level of stress is associated with decreased personal health and impaired individual functioning in the workplace in terms of decreased capacity to perform, dampened initiative and reduced interest in work, increased rigidity of thought, and a lack of concern for the organization and colleagues (e.g. Cooper and Marshall, 1976; Dua, 1994; Erkutlu and Chafra, 2006).

2.2 Work Schedule Flexibility

Work schedule flexibility refers to a policy in which the traditional fixed times that full-time employees start and finish the working day are replaced by a framework within which employees are allowed some freedom to choose their starting and finishing times (Golembiewski et al., 1975; Olorunsola and Ibegbulam, 2003). Work schedule flexibility is in operation as a part of the human resource benefit package offered to employees (Scandura and Lankau, 1997). The basic model of work schedule flexibility usually consists of five interrelated components although there are a number of variations in flexible time arrangements: (1) a band within which all hours must be worked (e.g. 6.00 am to 6.30 pm); (2) a core time during which all employees are required to be working (e.g. 10.00 am and 2.00 to 4.00 pm); (3) a flexible band of hours before, after, or in between core times that allows employees to exercise designated options regarding their presence in, or absence from, the work place; (4) banking, which allows a carry-over of surplus or deficient hours worked; and (5)

variability of schedule, i.e. the freedom of employees to vary working hours from one period to another without prior approval from their supervisor.

The availability of flexible work scheduling gives employees greater control over work and family matters, thereby helping employees to manage the often conflicting demands of work and non-work domains (Anderson et al., 2002). The work schedule flexibility is identified as the most frequently utilised and preferred arrangement by employees of the offshore outsourced software development industry in Sri Lanka (Jayabandu and Wickramasinghe, 2006). Jayabandu and Wickramasinghe (2006) also report that software developers experience a reduction in stress with the implementation of flexible work schedules. Therefore, in this study, work schedule flexibility is investigated as a form of instrumental support received formally through organizational initiatives, which could impact job stress experienced by employees.

2.3 Supervisor Support

Supervisor support describes the extent to which a supervisor is sensitive to an employee's non-work responsibilities and is accommodating when conflicting work and non-work demands arise (Carlson and Perrewé, 1999). Hence, scholars suggest that supervisor support may make one's work situation less stressful by providing emotional support, instrumental aid, or greater control over one's situation (e.g., Anderson et al., 2002; Carlson and Perrewé, 1999). Past researchers further suggested that support from one's supervisor is instrumental in reducing unfavourable effects of job stress by providing emotional support to increase the stressed individual's self-confidence (e.g., Russell et al., 1987; Wanniarachchi and Wickramasinghe, 2010) and self-esteem (e.g., Wong and Cheuk, 2005). Likewise, relevant and useful informational support from the supervisor helps the stressed individuals to cope effectively with job-related problems, which in turn reduces the job stress one is experiencing (Kumara and

Wickramasinghe, 2006; Thomas and Tymon, 1994).

2.4 Turnover Intention

Behavioural intentions constitute the most immediate determinant of actual behaviour, in the context of this study, employee turnover intention (e.g., Bluedorn, 1982; Dissanayake and Wickramasinghe, 2010). Steel and Ovalie (1984) showed the existence of a strong relationship between turnover intention and turnover. Some scholars (such as Bluedorn, 1982) recommended using intent to leave or intent to stay attitudes rather than actual staying or leaving behaviour, as collecting such information is relatively less expensive than collecting actual turnover. The literature suggests that workplace practices (such as work schedule flexibility and supervisor support) could reinforce employees' beliefs that the organization values their contribution and cares about their well-being, which in turn reduces turnover intention (Amarakoon and Wickramasinghe, 2010). Based on the aforementioned reasons, in this study, turnover intention is used as the dependent variable.

A number of studies indicated that IT personnel exhibit little loyalty to their organizations and may well be tempted to leave a firm for anticipated higher rewards elsewhere, as their skills are highly transferable across different firms and even different industries (Adya and Kaiser, 2005). Hence, organizations today find difficulties in attracting and retaining IT personnel. Studies that have examined the work in the outsourcing environment identify two common features of these organizations (Pearce, 1993). On the one hand, work in the outsourcing environment is highly monitored and controlled by management. On the other hand, these organizations consist of empowered workers who work in a positive work environment. These empowered workers customize work to the needs of customers (Batt and Appelbaum, 1995). Therefore, the work environment is highly controlled, and performance is closely monitored and measured against targets. However, employees are

encouraged to take responsibility for both their team's and their own performance (Frenkel et al., 1999). In this work environment, an important problem faced by the management is high labour turnover (Frenkel et al., 1999). The Sri Lankan outsourcing sector also suffers from high labour turnover (LIRNEasia, 2006).

2.5 Hypotheses

Drawing from the literature reviewed above, it is proposed for this study that the direct relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention will be mediated by job stress, and the direct relationship between supervisor support and turnover intention will be mediated by job stress. Figure 2.1 illustrates the proposed relationships.

Based on the conceptual framework developed for the study, the following hypotheses were proposed:

- H1a: Work schedule flexibility will be negatively related to turnover intention.
- H1b: Supervisor support will be negatively related to turnover intention.
- H2a: Work schedule flexibility will be negatively related to job stress.
- H2b: Supervisor support will be negatively related to job stress.
- H3: Job stress will be positively related to turnover intention.
- H4a: Job stress will mediate the relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention.
- H4b: Job stress will mediate the relationship between supervisor support and turnover intention.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

3. METHOD

3.1 Sample

A random sample of software developers attached full-time to offshore outsourced software development firms was selected. The list of software development firms registered and operating under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) was used. By the end of 2009, there were about 36 firms that were engaged purely in software development. Of the 350 questionnaires distributed among randomly selected individuals whose main job function is software development, 232 valid responses

were returned. The response rate was 66 per cent of the original sample.

With regard to the demographics of the respondents, 66% was male and 44% was female. 47% was single and 53% was married. The mean age was 30 years (SD=2.86; min.= 27 years; max.=40 years). The average number of years of service in the present firm was three years (SD=1.55; min=11 months; max=7 years); the average number of years of service in the IT industry was seven years (SD=1.94; min.= 11 months; max.=11 years). 83% had

Bachelor's degrees or equivalent professional qualifications; 17% had postgraduate degrees. 82% reported that they do not have dependents.

3.2 Data Collection Instrument and Measures

A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. In constructing the questionnaire, scale

items from existing research were used. Therefore, the content validity of the questionnaire was protected by embodying a sufficient number of items related to each variable in the study. The questionnaire was piloted prior to final distribution. The standardized estimates and reliability statistics for all the variables are provided in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Standardized Estimates and Reliability Statistics

	Standardised Cronbach's alpha	Eigenvalue	Explained variation	KMO sampling adequacy	Bartlett's Chi-Square
Job stress	.758	2.04	67.95	.519	99.42***
Turnover intention	.755	2.02	67.45	.641	76.86***
Supervisor support	.696	1.53	76.67	.521	59.64***
Work schedule flexibility	.717	1.93	64.49	.604	64.53***

Note: *** p<.001.

The constructs used in the questionnaire were as follows:

- Supervisor support was measured by the six items from Anderson et al. (2002). Respondents reported on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) very often to (1) never.
- Work schedule flexibility was measured by the three items that inquired into the level of usage of periodical flexi time, daily flexi time, and time off. Respondents reported on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) very often to (1) never.
- Job stress was measured using the five items from Lambert et al. (2006). Responses were reported on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) very often to (1) never.
- Turnover intention was measured by the four items from Bluedorn (1982). Respondents reported on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) very often to (1) never. The higher number indicates a higher level of quitting intention.

In the analysis, three demographic characteristics (gender, marital status, tenure) and one firm characteristic (firm size) were controlled. The demographic characteristics were gender (female=0, male=1), marital status (single=0, married=1), age (continuous scale), the highest level of education (degree or

equivalent=0, postgraduate degree=1), and the years of experience in the present workplace (continuous scale). In addition, firm size is also added as a control variable. Firm size was assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the number of full-time employees in the organization.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

The three-step regression analysis procedure recommended by Baron and Kenny (1986) was used to test mediation hypotheses. According to Baron and Kenny (1986), the following conditions must be met to support a mediating relationship. First, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the dependent variable. Second, the independent variable must be significantly associated with the mediator. Finally, after the mediator is entered, the relationship between the independent and dependent variables should either disappear (full mediation) or significantly diminish (partial mediation).

4. RESULTS

Table 4.1 shows means, standard deviations, and zero-order correlations between all the variables. As can be seen in Table 4.1, work schedule flexibility and supervisor support were negatively related to turnover intention. Job stress was positively related to turnover intention.

In analysing the mediator effect of job stress, the hypotheses were tested by estimating a series of multiple regression equations following the procedure presented in the section on “data analysis procedure”. The results are shown in Table 4.2 and Table 4.3. The results relating to work schedule flexibility-job stress-turnover intention relationship were shown in Table 4.2. As can be seen in Table 4.2, the conditions for mediation were met. Work schedule flexibility is significantly negatively associated with turnover intention, supporting H1a. Work schedule

flexibility is significantly negatively associated with job stress, supporting H2a. Job stress is significantly positively related to turnover intention, supporting H3. After job stress is entered, the relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention disappears ($\beta = -.272$, $p < .01$ to $\beta = -.201$, $p > .10$), suggesting full mediation. Critical ratios were also reported in Table 4.2. Accordingly, the mediation hypothesis (H4a) that job stress mediates the relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention is supported by the data.

Table 4.1 Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Gender ^a	.62	.49	1								
2 Age ^b	.38	.83	.221*	1							
3 Marital status ^a	.27	.44	-.042	.242*	1						
4 Education ^a	.16	.36	.109	.220*	-.072	1					
5 Tenure ^b	.28	.29	.112	.433**	.263*	-.008	1				
6 No. of employees ^b	.98	.51	.045	.052	.048	.091	.101	1			
7 Supervisor support	3.39	.75	-.027	.129	.104	.120	.115	.143	1		
8 Work schedule flexibility	3.26	.59	.185	.087	-.026	-.063	-.132	.203	-.212*	1	
9 Job stress	3.33	.74	-.154	-.088	.059	.043	-.054	-.112	-.349**	-.145	1
10 Turnover intention	3.21	.91	.167	-.051	-.009	.169	.085	-.132	-.409**	-.173	.301**

Notes: * significant at the .05 level (2-tailed), ** significant at the .01 level (2-tailed),

^a Binary-coded variables. ^b Log transformed

Table 4.2 Summarised results - job stress as a mediator in the work schedule flexibility and turnover intention relationship

Step	Variable	B	S.E.	β	R ² (Adj.)	F
1	<i>Controls</i> ^a					
	Gender	.301	.196	.162	.034	.784
	Age	-.043	.183	-.127		
	Marital status	-.050	.221	-.025		
	Highest level of education	.771	.134	.062		
	Tenure	.045	.064	.076		
	No. of employees	.051	.197	.027		
2	Work schedule flexibility → Turnover intention	-.421	.162	-.272**	.103	2.013**
3	Work schedule flexibility → Job stress	-.314	.134	-.270**	.165	1.217**
4	Work schedule flexibility → Turnover intention	-.311	.149	-.201	.266	5.252***
	Job stress → Turnover intention	.515	.117	.418***		

Sobel test $t = -2.068$ ($p = .038$), Aroian test $t = -2.028$ ($p = .042$), Goodman test $t = -2.111$ ($p = .034$), Direct effect $\beta = -.201$, Indirect effect $\beta = -.072$

Notes: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

^a Control variables were retained in the subsequent steps of 2, 3, and 4.

The results relating to supervisor support-job stress-turnover intention

relationship were shown in Table 4.3. As can be seen in Table 4.3, the conditions for

mediation were met. Supervisor support is significantly negatively associated with turnover intention, supporting H1b. Supervisor support is significantly negatively associated with job stress, supporting H2b. Job stress is significantly positively related to turnover intention, supporting H3. After job stress is entered, the relationship between supervisor support

and turnover intention significantly diminishes ($\beta = -.416$, $p < .001$ to $\beta = -.302$, $p < .01$), suggesting partial mediation. Critical ratios were also reported in Table 4.3. Accordingly, the mediation hypothesis (H4b) that job stress mediates the relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention is supported by the data.

Table 4.3 Summarised Results: Job Stress as a Mediator in the Supervisor Support and Turnover Intention Relationship

Step	Variable	B	S.E.	β	R ² (Adj.)	F
1	<i>Controls</i> ^a					
	Gender	.301	.196	.162	.034	.784
	Age	-.043	.183	-.127		
	Marital status	-.050	.221	-.025		
	Highest level of education	.771	.134	.062		
	Tenure	.045	.064	.076		
	No. of employees	.051	.197	.027		
2	Supervisor support → Turnover intention	-.495	.114	-.416***	.163	4.622**
3	Supervisor support → Job stress	-.353	.095	-.363***	.124	3.621**
4	Supervisor support → Turnover intention	-.360	.117	-.302**	.241	5.918***
	Job stress → Turnover intention	.385	.122	.314**		

Sobel test $t = -2.405$ ($p = .016$), Aroian test $t = -2.356$ ($p = .018$), Goodman test $t = -2.457$ ($p = .0139$), Direct effect $\beta = -.302$, Indirect effect $\beta = -.107$

Notes: ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

^a Control variables were retained in the subsequent steps of 2, 3, and 4.

5. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Organizations identify the need to address job stress. Drawing on previous research, this study investigated the effect of two major forms of support available in the organizational environment, i.e., instrumental support and social support, in reducing job stress and, in turn, reducing turnover intention. In the study, supervisor support is considered as an informal support, and work schedule flexibility as a formal policy initiative that could influence job stress and, in turn, turnover intention. The study treated work schedule flexibility and supervisor support as independent variables, job stress as a mediator, and turnover intention as a dependent variable.

The study investigated whether supervisor support mediates the positive relationship between job stress and turnover intention. It was found that job

stress partially mediates the relationship between supervisor support and turnover intention. Therefore, as expected, supervisor support was identified as an important support that serves as a mediator in the positive relationship between job stress and turnover intention. The findings support previous research that reported support from an immediate supervisor helps individuals to reduce stress (e.g., Anderson et al., 2002). Hence, the findings of the study imply the importance of a supportive organizational context created by the immediate supervisor in reducing job stress and, in turn, turnover intention.

Further, the study investigated whether work schedule flexibility mediates the positive relationship between job stress and turnover intention. It was found that job stress fully mediates the relationship between work schedule flexibility and turnover intention. Therefore, work schedule flexibility was also identified as

an important support that serves as a mediator in the positive relationship between job stress and turnover intention. The findings support previous research that reported the usage of flexible work scheduling helps individuals to reduce stress (e.g., Jayabandu and Wickramasinghe, 2006). Hence, the findings of the study imply the importance of supportive organizational policies (i.e., work schedule flexibility) in reducing job stress and, in turn, turnover intention.

In the current global economic environment, organizations are continually trying to discover value-added initiatives to strategically enhance the performance of their organizations and employees. Therefore, some of the most important topics of research in human resource management revolve around specific policies, practices, and programmes that appear to influence employee performance. Therefore, it is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information for both practitioners and academicians to better understand the nature of strategies to be adopted in offshore outsourced software development firms, as the results of the study implied that increased levels of supervisor support could lead to decrease job stress, which subsequently could lead to decreased turnover intention. Similarly, increased levels of work schedule flexibility could lead to decrease job stress, which subsequently could lead to decrease turnover intention.

REFERENCES

- Adya, M. and Kaiser, K.M. (2005). Early determinants of women in the IT workforce: a model of girls' career choices. *Information Technology & People*, 18(3): 230-259.
- Amarakoon, A. U. A. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2011). Effect of work, family, self, and social domains on work-life balance amongst managers in the private sector in Sri Lanka. *Annual Academic Sessions*, pp. 221-223. The Open University of Sri Lanka, September 14-15. http://repository.ou.ac.lk/bitstream/handle/94ousl/729/OU7276_000.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Amarakoon, A.U.A., and Wickramasinghe, V. (2010). Work-life balance beyond work and family domains. Proceedings of International Conference on Business and Information, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka, June 4.
- Anderson, S.E., Coffey, B.S. and Byerly, R.T. (2002). Formal organizational initiatives and informal workplace practices: links to work-family conflict and job-related outcomes. *Journal of Management*, 28(6): 787-810.
- Armstrong, G.S. and Griffin, M.L. (2004). Does the job matter? comparing correlates of stress among treatment and correctional staff in prisons. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 32(6): 577-592.
- Aziz, M. (2004). Role stress among women in the Indian information technology sector. *Women in Management Review*, 19(7): 356-363.
- Baron, R. and Kenny, D. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51: 1173-1182.
- Batt, R. and Appelbaum, E. (1995). Worker participation in diverse settings: does the form affect the outcome? If so, who benefits?, *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 33(3): 353-378.
- Bluedorn, A.C. (1982). A unified model of turnover from organizations, *Human Relations*, 35: 135-153.
- Burton, W.N., Schultz, A.B., Chen, C-Y. and Edington, D.W. (2008). The association of worker productivity and mental health: a review of the literature. *International Journal of*

- Workplace Health Management*, 1(2): 78-94.
- Carlson, D.S. and Perrewé, P.L. (1999). The role of social support in the stressor-strain relationship: an examination of work-family conflict. *Journal of Management*, 25(4): 513–540.
- Cooper, C.L. and Marshall, J. (1976). Occupational sources of stress: a review of the literature relating to coronary heart disease and mental ill health. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 49(1): 11-28.
- Dissanayake, D.M.M.M. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2010). A job satisfaction index to investigate the relationship between employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *Proceedings of International Conference on Business and Information*, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka, June 4.
- Dooris, M., Sedgley, L. and Dugdill, L. (2008). A reflective analysis of the development of a regional workplace health strategy in the North West of England. *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, 1(3): 209-218.
- Dua, J.K. (1994). Job stressors and their effects on physical health, emotional health, and job satisfaction in a university. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 32(1), 59-78.
- Erkutlu, H. V. and Chafra, J. (2006). Relationship between leadership power base and job stress of subordinates: example from boutique hotels. *Management Research News*, 29(5): 285-297.
- Frenkel, S., Korczynski, M., Shire, K. and Tam, M. (1999). *On the Front Line: Organization of Work in the Information Economy*. New York, NY: Cornell University Press.
- Golembiewski, R.T., Yeager, S. and Hilles, R. (1975). Factor analysis of some flexitime effects: attitudinal and behavioral consequences of a structural intervention. *Academy of Management Journal*, 18(3): 500-509.
- Jayabandu, S. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2006). Flexible work arrangements in software development companies in Sri Lanka. *Proceedings of 12th Symposium of Engineering Research Unit*, pp. 67-68, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka, November 29, ISSN 1391-3999.
- Jinadasa, L. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2005). IT industry labour turnover: the reality. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sri Lanka Studies*, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka, December.
- Johnson, S., Cooper, C., Cartwright, S., Donald, I., Taylor, P. and Millet, C. (2005). The experience of work-related stress across occupations. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 20(2): 178–187.
- Kumara, K.M.I.M. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2006). An application of two-factor theory to IT knowledge workers in Sri Lanka. *Proceedings of 3rd International Conference on Business Management*, pp. 107-111, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka, March 17, ISBN 955-9054-55-4.
- Lambert, E.G., Hogan, N.L., Camp, S.D. and Ventura, L.A. (2006). The impact of work–family conflict on correctional staff: a preliminary study. *Criminology and Criminal Justice*, 6(4): 371-387.
- Le Fevre, M., Kolt, G.S. and Matheny, J. (2006). Eustress, distress and their interpretation in primary and secondary occupational stress management interventions: which way first?. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21(6): 547-565.
- Le Fevre, M., Matheny, J. and Kolt, G.S. (2003). Eustress, distress, and interpretation in occupational stress.

- Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 18(7): 726-744.
- LIRNEasia (2006). *A baseline sector analysis of the business process outsourcing industry of Sri Lanka*, Colombo: Author.
- Olorunsola, R. and Ibegbulam, I.J. (2003). Flexible working hours for academic librarians in Nigeria. *Library Review*, 52(2): 70-75.
- Pearce, J.L. (1993). Toward an organizational behavior of contract laborers: their psychological involvement and effects on employee co-workers. *Academy of Management Journal*, 36(5): 1082-1096.
- Poravi, G. and Wickramasinghe, V.M. (2010). ICT employees' satisfaction with performance management systems in Sri Lanka. *5th International Conference on Information and Automation for Sustainability*, pp. 341-346, December 17-19, Sri Lanka.
- Russell, D.W., Altmaier, E. and Van Velzen, D. (1987). Job-related stress, social support, and burnout among classroom teachers. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 72(2): 269-274.
- Scandura, T.A. and Lankau, M.J. (1997). Relationships of gender, family responsibility and flexible work hours to organizational commitment and job satisfaction. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 18(4): 377-391.
- Scholarios, D. and Marks, A. (2004). Work-life balance and the software worker. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 14(2): 54-74.
- Steel, R.P. and Ovalie, N.K. (1984). A review and meta-analysis of research on the relationship between behavioural intentions and employee turnover. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 69: 673-686.
- Thomas, K.W. and Tymon, W.G. (1994). Does empowerment always work? understanding the role of intrinsic motivation and personal interpretation. *Journal of Management Systems*, 6(3): 1-13.
- Wanniarachchi, K.D.T., and Wickramasinghe, V. (2010). Causes and mediating effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on absenteeism and labour turnover in the Sri Lankan export apparel manufacturing industry. *Proceedings of International Conference on Business Management 2010*, pp. 85-100, Sri Lanka, May 14. <https://journals.sjp.ac.lk/index.php/icbm/article/view/761>
- Wong, K.S. and Cheuk, W.H. (2005). Job-related stress and social support in kindergarten principals: the case of Macau. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 19(3): 183-196.